

Regional Unemployment and Oil & Gas MNC's at Dadu: An Empirical Study of Human Resource Skills

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Mohsin Lund**-Pursuing Master of Business Administration (HR) From Muistd, Mehran University of Engineering and Technology Jamshoro. Email:mohsinbaloch633@gmail.com ⁽²⁾**Yasir Solangi**-Pursuing Master of Business Administration (HR) from MUISTD, Mehran University Jamshoro. Email: yasirali2309@gmail.com ⁽³⁾**Waqar Ahmed Sethar**-Lecturer Muistd, Mehran University of Engineering and Technology Jamshoro. Email:waqar.sethar@faculty.mueta.edu.pk ⁽⁴⁾ **Ayaz Rajab** - Loan Officer at khushali Bank, Dadu, Pakistan Email: Ayaz.rajab@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate of an increase in the regional unemployment through a comparison of required Human Resource Skills supply and its demand by the oil and gas multinational companies operating in district Dadu. The selected oil and gas company is Orient petroleum private limited for this study and three different educational institutes of Dadu including Ustad Bukhari Degree college Dadu, Sindh university campus Dadu, and Polytechnic institute Dadu. The nature of this research is qualitative so that two open ended semi-structured interviews was developed in order to collect data through audio recordings and transcribed into texts the data was further analyzed by the manifest content analysis technic. Study findings revealed the demand and supply of skills by the regional educational institutes and Demand of skills by the regional MNC orient petroleum on the basis of qualification, experience, soft and hard skills. Further the data was compared to regional MNC orient petroleum company and three different regional educational institutes.
Keywords: Regional unemployment, supply of skills, demand of skills, comparison of supply and Demand of skills, Skills Match and Mismatch

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Unemployment is defined by the American bureau of labor statistics the people who doesn't possess a job or willing to get a job since long time but they fail to get a desired job or people who were dismissed from the job they were not being called back to the job (Amadeo , 2018). This study primarily focuses on the increase in the regional unemployment specifically in Dadu region. District Dadu is the city of Sindh province which is located at the right bank of Indus River. The district was created in 1931 it has three Tehsils, Khairpur Nathan Shah, Mehar and Johi. The district is also rich in natural resource in 1998 the Australian based company discovered Pakistan's fourth largest Gas reserves in district Dadu and decided to invest 100 us million Dollar in first phase of the project. The project was proceeded as BHP Billiton (Zamzama) Gas field and later own its all shares was acquired by orient petroleum in 2015. The other huge crude oil and gas reserves was discovered by united Pakistan Energy Limited Mehar, However district Dadu is rich in natural resources the intentions or complaints of the regional people that these companies are hiring people out of the region from other provinces that the local people of District Dadu and its outskirts are being neglected from the job opportunities with an excuse from regional MNC's that regional people are non-skilled.

1.2 CAUSES OF UNEMPLOYMENT

Nationally, unemployment is exacerbated when the economy is backwards and by increment in labor expenditure, firms are empowered to deduct costs. Competition can also results in unemployment, in particular industries or businesses. High technology, such as computers or robots, creates unemployment by illuminating human-based jobs to machines.

Outsourcing jobs is a major cause of unemployment. The infrastructure, call centers and human resources are particularly common (Amadeo , 2018)

1.3 THE IMPACT OF UNEMPLOYMENT

The Impact of unemployment are financially and often emotionally devastating for the individual The economic impact can also be opposed if unemployment is higher than 5% or 6%. The economy lacks one of its key drivers of prosperity, consumer spending, when people are unemployed. Quite simply, there is less money for the workers to spend until they find another job. If high levels of national unemployment remain a recession can deepen, or even cause depression. Inferior consumer buying power from unemployed workers that inferior's business income, which enables Firms to decrease their expenses by cutting more payrolls. It can very fast develop into a downward spiral. (Amadeo , 2018)

1.4 INTERNATIONAL PERPECTIVE OF UNEMPLOYMENT

International labor organization assumes that unemployment is a state of being free and would like to work in any organization and unendingly looking for it since few weeks at the age of sixteen and above.

Nationally the reason of not getting a desired job that meet individuals standard and Qualification at the result on these consequences they decide to leave the job, It's not a healthy sign of any economy it cause impoverishment, crime, political and social unrest. (ILO, 1996)

Across the years, other less advanced countries and developing countries wants to wipe out the unemployment rate that appears to be quite prominent and common between these countries. He factors and reasons for that have persisted subject to various interpretations relying on the country's parameters, regional, and national populations, so the expectations of finding a plausible solution are lacking in concurrency. Not unexpectedly a large percentage amongst the other unemployed and victims belong to the young age group. (Siddiqui & Younis, 2019)

As per the International labor organization, there are 160 million unemployed in the world without exception, and not only have unemployment rates reached reasonable limits, but a large majority of them belong to the group of young people. (Labor Force Survey 2003-04, 2005-06).

Several major causes of unemployment have been identified by experts. Economic growth is the first factor that can impact the unemployment. Possibly, a high economic growth rate may reduce unemployment as businesses and the state in this phase become more powerful. To find out the connection between economic growth and unemployment, a number of studies have been carried out. It was believed, and demonstrated, that economic growth and unemployment had a negative relationship. (Fanati, 2003)

1.5 UNEMPLOYMENT IN PAKISTAN

The causes of this high youth unemployment lies in inadequate education, inadequate skills, systemic contradictions, disparity between urban and rural populations, inadequate experience, national or provincial wise disparities in the provision of employment opportunities, sectoral imbalances, etc. (Siddiqui & Younis, 2019)

1.6 UNEMPLOYMENT RATE IN PAKISTAN

1.7 REGIONAL UNEMPLOYMENT AND THE ROLE OF REGIONAL MNC'S IN DADU

District Dadu is rich in natural resources. In 1998 The Australian based company discovered Pakistan's fourth largest Gas Reserves in District Dadu and decided to invest 100 us million Dollar in first phase of the project. The project was proceeded as Zamzama Gas field and later on its all shares was acquired by orient petroleum in 2016. The other huge crude oil and gas reserves was discovered by United Energy Pakistan)., However District Dadu is rich in natural resources the intentions or complaints of the regional people that these companies are hiring people out of the region from other provinces that the local people of District Dadu and its outskirts are being neglected form the job opportunities which is the local people right.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

1.8 INTRODUCTION

The conceptual framework can be thought for planning the research and answering the research question. The research framework for this study is own compilation of the Author. Researchers mostly use the conceptual framework when existing theories aren't appropriate or acceptable in forming a firm structure for the study, according to this theory. (Akintoye, 2017)

Conceptual Framework provides direction and strategy that how each element or objective of study be achieved. Moreover it provides detailed relationship about that how each and every element or variable of research framework is related to one another. A conceptual framework is a framework that the researcher assumes best explains the logical progression of the phenomenon under study (Camp, 2001) Theoretical and conceptual frameworks direct the course of a study and provide the foundation for its validity. (Dickson & H, 2018)The link between a study's main concepts is described by the conceptual framework. It is organized in a logical intended to aid in the creation of a picture or visual representation of how well the ideas in a study relate with one another. (Grant, 2014)

A researcher can benefit from a conceptual framework in a number of ways. It aids the researcher, for example, in recognizing and creating his or her viewpoint on the phenomena being studied. (Grant, 2014)

A research's conceptual framework clarifies why a particular researcher chooses to study a particular or specific issue, the inferences he or she renders, how he or she embraces his or her approach, the authors with whom he or she is in discussion, and with whom he or she consented and disagrees. (Tamene, 2016)

This study implies conceptual framework which is authors own compilation, see Fig (1.0). It proposes demand of skills i.e. qualification and experience by the regional MNC’s and supply of skills i.e. qualification and Experience by the regional educational institutes.

Whereas magnitude of skills intends to interpret the data through the content analysis technique, where match of skills supplied and demanded will lead to employment and mismatch of skills supplied and demanded will lead to unemployment side each and every element of conceptual framework are illustrated in next section:

1.8.1 DEMAND OF SKILLS BY REGIONAL MNC’S

Demand of skills proposes the skills required by the regional multi-national companies the selected company for this study is Orient Petroleum Pty ltd (OPPL) Dadu, as demand of skills is independent variable because companies demand never changes. In this study the demand of skills and qualification is asked from the regional mnc’s employees regarding their experience criteria and Qualification through semi-structured interviews.

1.8.2 SUPPLY OF SKILLS BY THE REGIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTES

Supply of skills proposes skills generated by regional educational institutes, the selected educational institute for this study are University of Sindh Campus Dadu, Ustad Bukhari Degree College Dadu, and polytechnic institute Dadu. Hence supply of skills is a dependent variable because it is dependent on market job place demands. The data is gathered for this objective through semi-structured interviews from the employees of the three selected regional educational institutes.

1.8.3 MAGNITUDE OF SKILLS SUPPLIED AND DEMANDED

Magnitude of skills supplied and demanded refers the comparison of skills supplied between the regional MNC’s and regional educational institutes residing in District Dadu. This stage allows the researcher to assess the skills and qualification gape between the academia and market job place, hence the area of this study is orient petroleum Pty ltd Dadu (OPPL) and three different educational institutes of Dadu and further the data is analyzed with the method of manifest content analysis.

Conceptual Framework

Figurer 1.0

Literature Review

2.1 PERSPECTIVE OF UNEMPLOYEMENT

Unemployment differs from area to area, but it is usually seen mostly from a national perspective. There are at least three reasons to consider unemployment from a national viewpoint as well. Firstly, the magnitude of disparities in unemployment between regions within countries is nearly as large as the magnitude of differences in unemployment within countries respectively. (Elhorst, 2003)

2.2 COMPARISON OF UNEMPLOYEMENT BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL AREAS

When comparing urban areas on the outskirts of rural areas, it is evident that an every person or domestic worker from urban areas is reliable for raising the risk of unemployment by 1.3 per cent. The employment position in rural outskirts and urban areas varies considerably. Unemployment in urban areas is high in comparison with rural areas as implied by the extremely distinct result. The extreme level of unemployment in urban areas as compared to its outskirt rural areas is due to the organized incompatibility of expertise offered and needed (Siddiqui & Younis, 2019)

A further matter of serious concern is the local job. Fields of oil and gas are mostly located in distant and backward areas. Petroleum companies have head offices in big cities such as Islamabad and Karachi where local employees of Sindh barely make a small portion of their employment. Since Sindh is largest oil and gas producer in Pakistan and it is being neglected in employment opportunities (Memon, 2010)

2.3 EXCUSES OF REGIONAL MNCS IN SINDH

The oil and gas MNC's also make an excuse for not having qualified and experienced people from rural Sindh and Baluchistan. This claim has lost its relevance as the provinces now have a reputation for universities and technical institutes that produce large numbers of professionals with the requisite qualification. Unfortunately, these districts ' students do not even get incentives such as trainee management or auxiliary employees. Therefore trained youth of districts producing oil and gas are extracted from learning and opportunities in the businesses.. (Memon, 2010)

2.3.1 TABLE A: Statistics of local employment in a company:

Office	Total Employees	Local Staff
Islamabad	60	2 (3.3%)
Karachi	176	10 (5.6%)
Field	204	175 (85.7%)

(Memon, 2010)

2.3.2 TABLE B: Statistics of local employment in a company:

Office	Total Employees	Local Staff
Head Office	225	15
Field	300	20

(Memon, 2010)

2.4 IMPACT OF OVER EDUCATION ON UNEMPLOYMENT:

Educational incompatibility occurs in the form of over-education (i.e. workers have excessive education than their jobs require) or under-education (i.e. workers have less education than is required for their work). The vertical mismatch of education (the mismatch of education and employment levels) is not the only form of mismatch in education. Horizontal mismatch is another crucial form of mismatch. (M & z, 2013)

Research Materials and Methodology

2.5 Materials

In this study the targeted population was orient petroleum Pakistan limited (OPPL) Dadu a well reputed multinational company and also three different educational institutes of Dadu i.e. Sindh University Campus Dadu, Ustad Bukhari Degree College Dadu and Polytechnic Institute Dadu

Orient Petroleum Pty Limited is operating at Zamzama field that is located 10 km west of the city of Dadu in the Sindh Province, Pakistan. The field was discovered in 1998 and brought online in 2001.

2.6 Table C: (NUMBER OF INTERVIEWS)

NUMBER OF INTERVIEWS			
SR#	Data Sources	Interviews	Total Interviews
OB 1	Orient Petroleum (OPPL)	7	-----
OB 2	Degree College Dadu	5	-----
-----	Sindh University Campus Dadu	7	-----
-----	Polytechnic Institute Dadu	5	= 24

2.7 Methodology

The nature of this research is qualitative, So that in-depth semi-structured interviews through recording was held with orient petroleum companies employees and three different educational institutes of Dadu later on the Data was transcribed and analyzed with manifest content analysis technic.

2.8 QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

The analysis of qualitative data is initiated by transcribing the acquired data.

Therefore, the transcripts allows to help the researchers to fully understand the meaning of the answers given. For data analysis, the research uses the manifest content analysis technique. The analysis of data is divided into four parts: coding, sorting, sifting and formation of themes.

2.9 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Following themes are derived from the manifest content analysis of the acquired data, relevant to Objective 1:

3.1 OBJECTIVE 01

TO EXPLORE THE RECRUITMENT CRITERA OF THE SKILLED ABOUR FORCE IN MNC ORIENT PETROLEUM PTY LTD (OPPL)

The first objective of this research was to explore the recruitment criteria of skilled labor force from the MNC orient petroleum. In this objective we have conducted Structured Interviews in order asses information about recruitment method, Recruitment process of company either its directly or by third party the pre experience of employees recruited were asked after content analysis the result themes are given bellow.

3.1.1 METHOD OF RECRUITMENT ORIENT PETROLEUM

There are two methods of recruitment in this company one is for professional workers and second method is for non-professional skilled/ non-skilled workers which are recruited by third Party contractor e.g. (Dilshad & Sons)

Orient Petroleum recruits through online advertisement indirectly and in which candidates apply through company's website after that called for interview in the company.

3.1.2 RECRUITMENT CRITERIA

The recruitment criteria is specifically for professional worker and non-professional workers, it consist of qualification and experience required for professional administrative positions and for the technical and engineering workers.

3.1.3 RECRUITMENT CRITERIA FOR PROFESSIONAL WORKER

It is observed that permanent workers position at company are recruited directly by company these includes, Engineers, Human resource managers, admins, and accountants, assistant. Auditors and clerks.

3.1.4 EXPERIENCE REQUIRED FOR ADMINISTRATIVE POSITIONS

It's evident that analyzed from the interviews conducted from supervisor and admin of orient petroleum that they are qualified from university and had prior work experience of more than one year In reputed industry hence its risky for a company to higher fresh graduates with lower skills they need further training becomes more costly while experienced employees are cost effective.

3.1.5 EXPERIENCE REQUIRED FOR TEHNICAL AND ENGINEERING POSITIONS

Its observed from semi-structured interviews that civil supervisor engineer and other technicians working at orient petroleum, possess prior experience work of more than two years in well reputed industry and possess knowledge about operating modern electronic devices used by the industry, Hence it is risky for companies to recruit non experienced engineers and other technical staff so that leads to risk of fire and other loss of company.

3.1.6 NON-PROFESSIONAL WORKERS

Non-skilled and skilled workers are hired by third party contractors which are divide into two categories

3.1.7 SKILLED WORKERS

Skilled workers are contract based workers which are basically drivers and security guards these are hired by third party contractors next to orient petroleum company. e.g. (Dilshad & Sons). While it's also observed that security guards possess experience of more than one year, they were retired army personal and matric pass.

3.1.8 NON-SKILLED WORKERS

Non skilled workers are contract based workers which are labors and helpers hired by third party contractors next to orient petroleum private ltd. e.g. (Dilshad & Sons).

3.1.9 JOB FAIR BY ORIENT PETROLEUM AND PREFERENCE OF LOCAL FOR RECRUITMENT

Orient Petroleum doesn't conduct any type of job fairs either regionally or nationally, Hence no evidence found for job fair by the regional company for the recruitment of local people but the preference of recruitment for the regional people except non-skilled workers and skilled workers were given, Because they were recruited on the basis of land owners the land which is under usage of orient petroleum company.

3.2 RECRUITMENT CRITERIA OF ORIENT PETROLEUM AND THIRD PARTY (Assessed from the collected data.)

3.2.1Table C: (Recruitment Criteria by Orient Petroleum)

Recruitment Criteria of Professional Positions		
Designation	Required skills or Experience	Qualification
Admin	2 years	MBA\BBA \B.COM
HR Manager\ Assistant HR Manager	2 years or more	MBA HR/BBA HR

Finance Manager Assistant finance Manager	2 years or more experience in managing salaries, forecasting and cost analysis of purchases	MBA\ BBA FINANCE
Mechanical Engineer Assistant Mechanical Engineer	3 years or more in well reputed industry	ME MECHANICAL BE MECHANICAL DAE MECHANICAL
Electrical Engineer Assistant Electrical Engineer	3 years or more in reputed industry	ME ELECTRICAL ME ELECTRICAL
Accountant	1 years in handling of accounts e.g.(petty cash Book)	B.COM

3.2.2 Table D: (Recruitment criteria by Third Party Dilshad & Sons)

Recruitment Criteria of Skilled and NON-Skilled workers		
Designation	Required Experience and skills	Qualification
Guards	At least 1 year Experience or Preference will be given to retired army Personal	MATRIC PASS
Drivers	Having valid Driving License and experience of at least 1 year.	MATRIC PASS OR PRIMARY PASS
Labor	Preference of Local /Experience is not Required	PRIMARY PASS

3.3 DATA ANALYSIS OBJECTIVE 2

The second objective of this research was to investigate the required skills of graduates from the skill generating institutes Dadu (i.e. Degree College Dadu, Polytechnic Institute Dadu, Sindh University Campus Dadu) data was collected through structured Interview Questionnaire in order to assess information about Degrees Offered by The Institutes, Internship Experience, and Soft Skills offered to graduates. After the Content analysis the themes are given in next section:

4.1 THEMES OF OBJECTIVE 2 (DEGREE COLLEGE DADU)

4.1.1 DEGREES OFFERED AT DEGREE COLLEGE DADU

Degree College Dadu offers two-year degree program including B.com, Ba and BSc. The college was affiliated with university of Sindh before 2015 after then affiliation transferred to Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University Nawabshah in 2016.

4.1.2 NUMBER OF ADMISSIONS AND GRADUATES

Degree College was affiliated with university of Sindh before 2015 the number of admissions was 5000 after transfer the affiliation of college to Shaheed Benazir

Bhutto University Shaheed Benazir Abad the Number of admission reduced to 500 due to their limitation of seats and now number of graduates is about 400.

4.1.3 EXPERIENCE

4.1.4 INTERNSHIP EXPERIENCE

There is no requirement of an internship for the degree completion at Degree College Dadu. However, conduct of activities like workshops and seminars that enables students to participate in speech competition these include computer skills, communication skills that help student in career counseling.

4.1.5 JOB FAIR BY REGIONAL MNC'S

All the respondents of Degree College were asked about regional recruitment of local graduates, but they have not claimed and supported this argument that regional MNC's conduct Job Fair for the recruitment of local people.

4.1.6 SCHOLARSHIPS

According to Employees of Degree College Dadu Regional MNC's and NGO's offer scholarships for the regional talented poor students who doesn't afford higher studies.

5.1 THEMES OF OBJECTIVE 2 (SINDH UNIVERSITY CAMPUS DADU)

5.1.1 DEPARTMENTS AT SINDH UNIVERSITY CAMPUS:

University of Sindh Campus Dadu has "3" main departments. Including Faculty Business Administration, English and Information Technology.

5.1.2 DEGREE PROGRAMS

There are four kinds of degree programs are being offered, Including MBA, BBA, BS English and BS Information Technology (IT).

5.1.3 DURATION OF DEGREES AND NUMBER OF ADMISSIONS

Duration of Degree is four years at this campus however the number of admissions is about 280 totally.

5.1.4 NUMBER OF SEATS AND GRADUATES

Totals number of seats at Sindh university campus Dadu is 280 from which 50 are for each department including, 60 for BBA, 60 for BS English and 60 for BS information Technology (IT) where as the number of seats for MBA is 60 and 10 reserved for self-finance basis. However the total number of graduates is about 230 according to head clerk Sindh university campus Dadu.

5.1.4.1 TABLE E: Number of seats in each discipline (Sindh University Campus Dadu)

Department /faculty	Number Of Seats	Number Of Seats Self Finance	Total Number Of seat Each Department	Total Number OF Seats
MBA	60	10	70	280
BBA	60	10	70	
BS English	60	10	70	
BS Information Technology(IT)	60	10	70	

5.1.5 EXPERIENCE

Experience beside academic work plays role in strengthening students' professional background, and Knowledge, these includes Workshops, and Seminars are being carried out at Sindh University campus Dadu. One third of employers would flatly reject graduate applicants that don't even have at last a year's worth of job experience beneath the belts coming out of higher education, as per studies done by High Fliers. (Fliers, 2018)

5.1.6 INTERNSHIP EXPERIENCE

According to Sindh university campus Dadu it's compulsory requirement as per HEC policy for final year students to fulfil requirement of their degree, however students are entitled to go for internship at their field of study and Many of students go under internship programs offered at various organizations in government as well as private sector e.g. PTCL, Banks, SECP, PIA and other organizations. According to HEC (In order to graduate, every graduate student have to complete an internship program, of at least 9-week duration, at any time after the completion of their fourth semester, generally during the summer vacations. Universities will collaborate with employers to arrange the requisite number of internship slots. (HEC, 2020)

5.1.7 SOFT SKILLS

According to employees of Sindh university campus Dadu, they had following facilities, general computer lab and specific IT lab for students and more over they have been providing many books, Magazines, Newspaper at their own library for the enhancement of soft skills of their students. Soft skills are different from technical skills this include how you communicate with other people.

How you resolve issues while you're doing your job. (South Dakota Department of Education., 2020)

5.1.8 TYPES OF SKILLS

Soft skills include the personal characteristics, personality Characteristics, and communication skills necessary for workplace success. Soft abilities describe how a person communicates with others in their relationships, soft abilities include ability

To adapt, communication, creativity, efficiency, work ethic, teamwork, positive attitude, time management, inspirational, and problem solving. (South Dakota Department of Education., 2020)

5.1.9 JOB FAIR BY REGIONAL MNC'S DADU

All the current respondents of Sindh university campus were asked about local recruitment of local graduates by the regional MNC's but they have not claimed and supported this argument that regional MNC's conduct Job Fair for the recruitment of local people.

6.1 THEMES OF OBJECTIVE 2 (POLYTECHNIC INSTITUTE DADU):

6.1.1 DEGREE PROGRAMS

Government polytechnic institute Dadu is offering four Degree programs these are DAE (civil, Electrical, CIT, Software Technology) and one year courses including, graphic designing and Navtec.

6.1.2 NUMBER OF ADMISSIONS

The number of admissions is about 500, however the number of graduate this year is about 400.

6.1.3 DURATION OF DEGREE

There are four degree programs are offered by this institute including for three years DAE (civil, Electrical, CIT, Software Technology) including two course programs are of one year duration, graphics designing and Navtec.

6.1.3 DEGREE SCOPE

According to employees of Polytechnic Institute Dadu, their graduates are well competent because they learn practical work beside theory they can apply in any engineering field inside or outside the country, government sector and private sector as well.

6.2 INFRASTRUCTURE

At Polytechnic institute Dadu All the facilities are available that could be in reputed universities, Polytechnic Institute Dadu have well equipped lab with 40 computers including projectors and other devices for the improvement of their technical skills, polytechnic college also have workshops inside college for practical work beside theory.

6.3 INTERNSHIP EXPERIENCE

Students of this college doesn't need of internship for degree completion, however when they graduate they are offered course by NAVTEC, we engage most of students in practical workshops inside the institute through the course including letter writing, Computer skills, study tour in industries that enhance student's practical knowledge that leads to career development.

6.3.1 SOFT SKILLS

This institute conduct extra lab work that enhance students soft skills as well as hard skills these include, Computer skills, Writing skills, communication skills including verbal and writing skills and other practical workshops.

6.3.2 STUDY TOURS EXPERIENCE

Polytechnic institute Dadu conducts study tour every year for the enhancement of students practical knowledge, hence it's all about what is going inside the firms and industries these study tour help student to get insight about industry.

6.4 WORKING IN MNCS

There is no evidence seen on the behalf of graduates for polytechnic college for working at regional MNC's.

6.5 JOB FAIR

No Job Fair took place at Dadu by the regional MNC's for the recruitment regional graduates.

7.1 OBJECTIVE 3 (A comparison of the current regional skills level with the demand of skills by the selected oils and gas MNCs)

Comparison of the Current Regional Skills Level with The Demand of Required Skills by the Selected Oil and Gas Petroleum Company, At this stage data is derived from the findings of objective 1, the recruitment criteria from oil and gas MNC (orient petroleum Pty ltd) (OPPL) Dadu and from objective 02 to investigate the required skilled level from educational institute Dadu demanded by the regional MNC Orient Petroleum. After the analysis of the data from objective 01 and objective 02, here content analysis of skills demand and supply comparison will take place.

7.2 Table F: (Magnitude of skills, supply by University of Sindh Campus Dadu vs Skills Demand by MNC Orient Petroleum)

Magnitude of skills, supply By University Of Sindh Campus Dadu vs Skills Demand by MNC Orient Petroleum		
Demand Of Skills By Orient Petroleum	Skills Match \Mismatched	Supply of skills By Regional Educational Institutes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree\Qualification • 1 year Experience • Soft Skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matched • Mismatched • Mismatched 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree\Qualification • 3 Months Internship • In adequate soft skills

7.3 Table G: (Magnitude of Skills, Supply by Polytechnic Institute Dadu vs Demand of Skills by MNC Orient Petroleum)

Magnitude of Skills, Supply By Polytechnic Institute Dadu vs Demand of Skills By MNC Orient Petroleum.		
Demand Of Skills By Orient Petroleum	Skills Match\ Skills Mismatch	Supply Of skills By Regional Educational Institute
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree\Qualification • Experience 1 to 2 years • Soft Skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matched • Mismatched • Matched 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree\Qualification • No Professional Experience • Communication Skills, Computer Skills

7.4 Table H: (Magnitude of skills Supply by Degree College Dadu vs Demand of skills by Orient Petroleum)

Magnitude of skills Supply By Ustad Bukhari Degree College Dadu vs Demand of skills By Orient Petroleum		
Demand Of Skills By Orient Petroleum	Skills Match\ Skills Mismatch	Supply Of skills By Regional Educational Institute
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree\Qualification • Experience 1 to 2 years • Soft Skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matched • Mismatched • Matched 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree\Qualification • No Professional Experience • Communication skills

8.1 Discussion:

1. Orient Petroleum recruits through online advertisement indirectly and in which candidates apply through company's website after that called for interview in the company.
2. Employees of orient Petroleum were qualified from experience based university and had prior work experience of more than one year In reputed industry hence its risky for a company to higher fresh graduates with lower skills they need further training becomes more costly while experienced employees are cost effective.
3. Employees of orient petroleum possess prior experience work of more than two years in well reputed industry and knowledge about operating modern electronic appliances used by the industry hence its risky for companies to recruit non experienced engineers and other technical staff so that leads to risk of fire and other loss of the concerned company.
4. It's observed that Non-skilled and skilled workers are hired by third party contractors next to orient Petroleum Company it includes Drivers, security guards, Security Supervisors and labors.
5. It's observed that for the recruitment security guards and security supervisor require experience for more than one year and preference is given to army retired personals.
6. No evidence found for job fair by the company for the recruitment of local people but the preference of the recruitment of regional people only for non-skilled workers and skilled workers, because they were recruited on the basis of land owners the land which is under usage of orient petroleum company.

7. Qualification is matched for the administration positions i.e. accountant, auditor, clerk and admin hence Degree college Dadu is offering two years degree B.com, BA and BSC.
8. Degree College Dadu has no condition of internship for degree completion so that students do not have professional experience except attending of seminars and workshops is not enough and clear that students participate in these events.
9. Activities like workshops and seminars that enables students to participate in speech competition these include computer skills, communication skills that help student in career counseling.
10. It's observed that Degree College Dadu offers 2 years degree program including B.COM, BA and BSC.
11. It's observed that number of students is about 500 and the number of graduates for the year 2020 is 400.
12. It's observed that Degree College has no condition of internship for degree completion so that students do not have professional experience except attending of seminars and workshops is not enough and clear that students participate in these events.
13. No evidence found regarding employment of regional graduates found for recruitment in MNC's.
14. It's observed that regional MNC's conduct test of students in colleges and award scholarships to regional talented students.
15. It's observed that Sindh university campus Dadu offers four years Degree program including BBA, MBA in (HR/Finance/Marketing) and BS English and BS (IT) Disciplines.
16. It's Observed that as per higher Education Commission (HEC) its compulsory requirement for degree completion that every final year student to go for internship and time allowed for internship is from six weeks during summer vacations Many of students of this campus go under internship programs offered at various organizations in government as well as private sector e.g. PTCL, Banks, SECP, PIA and other organizations for the period of three months during summer vacations.
17. There were no evidence found for soft skills, providing books, specific IT Lab, News Paper, and computer lab and Magazines would not alone improve soft skills of students.
18. No evidence found that MNC's conduct job fair for the recruitment of regional graduates.
19. The degree or qualification requirement for supply and demand is matched for technical positions, however Government polytechnic institute is offering qualification in these degrees including DAE in (Electrical\civil\Software Technology)
20. Professional experience is needed for engineering posts at least 1 or 2 years, however experience is mismatched in the sense of having no any knowledge about operating Company's modern machines
21. Soft skills are matched with the Demand of company soft skills are comprises of cation, writing and interpersonal skills.

CONCLUSION

8.2 CONCLUSION

The main aim of this study was to explore the causes of regional unemployment through the demand of skills by regional MNC's and supply of skills by the regional educational institutes. Here the research work concluded the findings.

For this study orient petroleum Dadu was selected and three different regional educational institutes of Dadu were selected including Sindh university campus, Ustad Bukhari Degree College, and polytechnic institute

Dadu in this study it is analyzed that regional MNC's require qualified and experienced based persons for their permanent positions in company including engineering and technical positions with minimum 3 years' experience. Moreover For administrative positions the experience of more than one year and qualification is required.

In the last objective of this research data was compared with educational institutes of Dadu and Sindh university campus Dadu. Where it is observed that for administrative position, e.g. clerk, admin, HR manager and auditor experience of at least one year was required which is mismatched by Sindh university campus Dadu and also soft skills were mismatched as it can be seen in table G.

The findings revealed for technical and engineering positions e.g. electrical engineer, mechanical engineer, technicians and other technical workers their qualification is matched but their experience is mismatched by the polytechnic institute Dadu as it can be seen in Table H.

Today many educational institutes not only in Dadu but entire country produces thousands of graduates, hence the graduates' first priority is to apply for government job because it's more secure than the private, only few of graduates make hardly a room. Beside this thousands of graduates becomes deprived and unemployed.

When fresh graduates go for applying in private firms many conditions comes around them, including professional experience and expertise is required therefore it's hardly found that firms recruit fresh graduates. Hence on this main cause this research was conducted, this study analyzed that colleges, universities, and all the degree offering institutes only focus on their academic and theory work but not on professional skills that leads path to career after graduation As per HEC policy universities allow only 6 to 9 weeks internship programs that help to develop professional skills of the students but three months period is not enough, it should be extended minimum of one year as mandatory for partial requirement of Degrees. Moreover companies do not often higher fresh and UN experienced individuals because it's more costly to train fresh graduates which is risky for firms.

8.3 PRACTICAL CONTRIBUTION OF THIS RESEARCH STUDY

This research study contributes practical experience on ground realities about what it has been offered in the regional educational institutes as well as entire the country. Today many universities and colleges produce thousands of graduates but majority of them are unemployed due to lack of expertise, lack of practical knowledge and experience. This study also contributes demand and supply of skills between academia and market job place, most of the companies and firms demand highly skilled workers that can be cost be effective and require no more training that may be decline of a company or a firm.

8.4 RECOMENDATIONS

8.4.1 RECOMMENDATION FOR ACADEMIA

Academia should not only focus on academic work of students, but it should be extended more to professionalism, by updating their curricular and by conducting extra classes that enhance students soft and hard skills as well these include interpersonal skills, communication skills, and hard skills like computer skills practical workshops etc.

8.4.2 RECOMMENDATION FOR HEC

Higher education commission (HEC) policy only allows 6 to nine weeks internship duration, but it should be extended to minimum one year and moreover it should be mandatory requirement for graduation

8.4.3 RECOMMENDATION FOR GOVERNEMENT OF PAKISTAN

Its hereby recommended to government of Pakistan that thousands of students are being graduated every year but only a small portion of graduates make a portion for employment in government sector, But private sector is neglecting the fresh graduates on the basis of experience, so that government should focus on amendment in legislation about private sector and direct private companies to hire fresh graduates and training costs should be bearded by government or may government offer subsidies to companies.

8.4.4 LIMMITATION AND FUTURE STUDY DIRECTION

This study is limited to only one regional oil and Gas Company, hence it can be extended, because not every researcher nor have time neither resources that can collect the data. Moreover this research is only limited to employees of educational institutes but it can be extended to students and graduates in order to assess deeply insight about the experience and expertise they might have possessed after graduation.

References

- i. Akintoye, A. (2017, 03 07). *Developing Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks*. Retrieved from Jedm.oauife.edu.ng: Jedm.oauife.edu.ng
- ii. Amadeo . (2018). *American Bureau of Labor Statistics. Washington,Dc: The Balance*. Retrieved from <https://www.thebalance.com/what-is-unemployment-3306222>
- iii. Bullen, E. (2015). *Indices of Deprivation. Public Intelligence Performance, Research and Intelligence (PRI) , Chief Executive's Department , Manchester*.
- iv. Delahunt, M. M. (2017). *Doing a Thematic Analysis: A Practical, Step-by-Step Guide for Learning and Teaching Scholars.*. ALL IRELAN JOURNAL OF TEACHING AND LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION*.
- v. Dickson, D., & H, E. K. (2018). *THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: MANDATORY INGREDIENTS OF A QUALITY RESEARCH. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH*.
- vi. Elhorst, J. P. (2003). *THE mystery of regional unemployment deprivation differentials: Theoretical and emperical explanations. JOURNAL OF ECONOMIC SURVEYS Vol. 17, No. 5, 7(5)*.
- vii. Fanati, L. a. (2003). *Population,Unemployment and Economic Growth Cycles:A further Explanatory Perspective",. Metroeconomica*.
- viii. Fliers, H. (2018). *The Graduate Market. London: High Fliers Research Limited*.
- ix. Grant, C. &. (2014). *Understanding, Selecting, and Integrating a Theoretical Framework in Dissertation Research: Creating the Blueprint for 'House'. Administrative Issues Journal: Connecting Education, Practice and Research, 12-22. doi:DOI: 10.5929/2014.4.2.9*
- x. HEC. (2020). *Undergraduate Education Policy. Islamabad: Higher Education Commission Pakistan*.
- xi. ILO. (1996). *International Labor Organization (1996)*. Retrieved March 14, 2014 , from from <http://www.ilo.org/global/lang--en/index.htm>
- xii. Julia, B. (2008). *First steps in qualitative data analysis: transcribing. Family Practice, 127-131*.
- xiii. K. Hammarberg1, *. M. (2016). *Qualitative research methods: when touse them and how to judge them. Advance acces Publication*.
- xiv. Lgwenagu. (2016). *Fundamentals of research methodology and data collection. LAP Lambert Academic Publishing*.

- xv. M, U. U., & z, N. (2013). *Educational Mismatch between Graduates Possessed Skills and Market Demands in Pakistan*. *International Education Studie*.
- xvi. Mary, D. (2018, June 25). *Advantages & Disadvantages of Qualitative & Quantitative Research*. Retrieved January 25, 2021, from <https://www.theclassroom.com/advantages-disadvantages-of-qualitative-quantitative-research-12082716.html#:~:text=A%20big%20advantage%20of%20qualitative%20research%20is%20the,instante.%20Examples%20include%20ethnography%2C%20narratives%20and%20grounded%20t>
- xvii. Memon, N. (2010). *Oil & Gas Resources and Rights of Provinces- A case study of Sindh*. Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan: Center for Peace & Civil Society. Retrieved from <http://www.cpcs.org.pk/>
- xviii. Moortel, H. P., C, V., & s, G. (2018, February). *Employment status and mortality in the context of high and low regional unemployment levels in Belgium (2001–2011): A test of the social norm hypothesis across educational levels*. PONE. Retrieved from Published
- xix. Siddiqui, R., & Younis, W. (2019). *Regional Unemployment*. Management.
- xx. South Dakota Department of Education. (2020, June 13). *South Dakota Department of Education*. Retrieved 13 June 2013, from <https://doe.sd.gov/CTE/softskills.aspx>
- xxi. Tamene, E. H. (2016). *THEORIZING CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK*. *Asian Journal of Educational Research*, 02.
- xxii. Terell, K., & Jurajda, S. (2007). *Regional Unemployment and Human Capital in Transition Economies*. Discussion Paper Series, 41.
- xxiii. Tordo, S., Warner, M., Manzano, O., & Anouti, Y. (2013). *Local Content Policies in The Oil and Gas Sector*. The World Bank. © 2013 International Bank for Reconstruction and Development Washington DC: International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank. Retrieved from www.worldbank.org